

THE SPIRITUAL WORLD OF HUMAN BEINGS IN THE STORIES OF FAZLIDDIN MUHAMMADIEV

¹Abdueva M., ²Kurbanalieva M.S.

¹Student of the 3rd year of the department Tajik, Faculty of Russian Philology and
Languages Eastern Termiz State University

²Scientific leader: senior teacher (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11622711>

Abstract. *Fazliddin Mohammadiev was one of such skilled writers who fought for the purity of society, for the unshakable morality, for raising the spirituality of man with his works. The article talks about the spiritual world of man in the writer's stories "Roh", "Cure", "Sozi Nawvar", "Funeral Day of Master Wise", "Court of Friends". In the stories of Fazliddin Mohammadiev, he mostly portrays the beauty and beauty of the human world. The struggle of the writer is for the purity of the society, for the moral integrity and spirituality of a perfect human being.*

Keywords: *Fazliddin Mohammadiev, spirituality, stories, the inner world of man, morality.*

...Spirituality is the power that affects the human consciousness and directs his worldview and way of thinking in a certain direction. A society that has spirituality and knowledge and is aware of its history and past always matures and has a great future.

Our ancestors defined literature-humanities, poets and writers as engineers of the human soul. Of course, this is not without reason, because our literature illuminates the path of each of us through its precious works. In our modern literature, there are writers who, as rhetoricians and psychics, were able to depict the inner world of man.

Fazliddin Mohammadiev was one of such skilled writers who fought for the purity of the society, for the unshakable morality, for raising the spirituality of man with his works. The writer lived in an environment where life was full of struggles, and he drew deep social and philosophical conclusions from these daily life events, forcing one to think.

Famous critic, friend and colleague of F.Mohammadiev in his article, "Eternal life is in the heart of life", Mohammadiev Jurakhan Bakozada said about the writer: "...the teacher had a meek and attractive face, a gentle smile and a sly look. Everyone, who once got to talk to that person, wished to have a conversation with such a person at least one more time. ...However, the teacher's stories and stories were not just for the sake of momentary entertainment, but had a purpose and were told with a certain purpose and intention. In every case and situation, words were a weapon, a sharp weapon for him..."(1, p. 574) These thoughts about the writer were rightly said, he had exactly such qualities.

The first book of Fazliddin Mohammadiev under the title "Mohajiron" was published in 1958. From the essays and stories of this collection, it appears that a talented writer has entered the world of literature; a writer who has a passionate heart, delicate humor, worldview and a higher theme, his language and manner of expression are clean and smooth, and the reader's love for the writer grows stronger and stronger from one book to another.

It can be said that the central theme of Fazliddin Mohammadiev's creativity is human morality. In this context, his series of stories "Claim" (1967), "Court of Friends" (1967), "The

Day of Master Aqil's Burial", "Sozi Munawvar" (1967), "Khiyaboni Nadir" and "The Third Night" (1973) were created. . All the heroes of these stories are discussed through psychological imagery, because it has been proven that psychological imagery serves to fully and clearly reveal human insight, human heartbreak, and also provides many opportunities to show various aspects of the hero's relationship with the environment in which he acts. makes (6, P.59). In these works, Fazliddin Mohammadiev describes the relationship and interaction of the hero in the family, with friends and comrades, with those around him, and his thoughts and observations. Fazliddin Muhammadiev was able to take advantage of his innate talent, create a complete character in his stories, create a clear spiritual world and character of the hero (3, 84). Fazliddin Mohammadiev mostly accepts the image of beauty and comfort of the inner and outer world of man. In the image of the writer, although the hero has many bad, negative qualities, it is imagined that he is not negative. The writer skillfully condemns this or that inappropriate behavior of some people, such as the stinginess of Muhammad Murad from the story "Claim", the unreasonable jealousy of Ashraf from the story "Sauda Ummer", the failure to inherit his carpentry profession from Master Aqil from the story "The Day of Burial of Master Aqil", because such aspects do not correspond to human morality (4, P.198). Another aspect of Fazliddin Mohammadiev's creative work is in the exciting and bright image, in the intensity of problem-solving, clarity of thought and activity of his characters. The works of a sensitive writer make the reader think about who he is, and in this way they plant seeds of goodness in his heart. This, of course, requires both talent and effort from the writer. F. Muhammadiev knows that a good work will only come out if both of these - talent and hard work - come together.

We now recall some of the writer's stories. For example, the story "The Road" [2, P.4-20]. In this story, the details of the journey of a village girl named Fatima, who studies in the capital's high school, are described. Coincidentally, the girl is driving the road to her hometown of Farkhor in a truck at night. He sits alone next to the driver, who is a man of few words and very serious, and he thinks with fear - it was completely foolish for him to go on a trip at this time, in case the "thief" driver had bad intentions towards him! The night is dark, the road is far, lonely... (2, p. 15).

But the driver can't imagine that the girl is suspicious of him. Because his intentions are pure, he knows the value of humanity, which the writer also raised in his story. Therefore, in order to bring the girl home safely, he joins hands with one or two of his colleagues. For him, the honor and pride of a person is more important than anything, even his own safety. One reads the story and comes to the conclusion: the character of Fatima, who is a girl with a good spirit and a lover of life, takes a serious shape after this dangerous night of the journey. At the end of that dark and terrifying night, she finds in her heart not only trust, but also a kind of faith in people. He promises himself that in the future, if necessary, he can fight for human dignity like that driver. And the writer himself also has such an opinion in his works; he dreams of people who believe in love, loyalty and masculinity, in the high spirit of man. (2, P.17; 4, P.96)

The main theme of the stories of the famous writer Fazliddin Mohammadiev "Court of Friends", "Claim", "The Funeral of Usta Aqil", "Khiyobani Nadir" and "Jaga" is also social morality. The writer expertly explored the inner world of his characters and created memorable and psychologically strong characters. For example, if Master Aqil from the story "The Day of the Funeral of Master Aqil" despite his hard work and talent, is a self-centered and isolated person, and because of this, he buried the secret of his art, which is extremely necessary for the

people, along with the shroud, and caused the people's just verdict, then Ahmedbeki The wrestler from the story "Claim" is a person who embodies many good human qualities, he is always a partner in people's sorrows and joys, he does not lose his composure and patience even in the most difficult situations. Ahmadbek, because he is not good in front of him, does not want to bury the secrets of his art like Master Akil. Therefore, he is happy with the wrestling of young Mohammad Murad, like a father with the fame of his son. And even when he reprimands him for his rudeness, he reprimands him in a secluded corner, alone and fatherly. Because he does not want the people to turn their backs on Muhammad Murad and the province to be left without fighters (2, P.77-90).

Another story of the author is called "On the shore of the lake". The story goes like this: "Many children are swimming in the lake. The sounds of laughter, play and their joyous jumping made the atmosphere of the mountain valley rumble. An old man sits on the green grass far from the beach and sunbathes his half-naked body. Next to him is a pair of boots. He slowly raises his trouser leg, rubs his wooden sock and looks longingly at the clear water of the lake. A few jet planes make white streaks in the sky; Curved, straight, round stripes. On the other hand, the stripes fall into the clear water, and the morson jumps and crawls. The man stares at the sky for a while. He smiles when he sees a bright spot behind which a clean white streak appears. Then he looks again at the children playing, and the smile disappears from his face. A veil of imagination covers his eyes" (3, p. 41). In this story, as in the picture, there is everything you need. Both the result of the war, and our happy life, both the happy children of the era and - the most important thing - the threat of a new war! Such fragments of the psychological landscape are found in almost every work of the writer and cause the events to come out in a powerful way.

Again F. Mohammadiev was a master in creating the image of gray-haired people, those who have lived a long life and know well the ups and downs of life. He often portrays elderly people in a certain period of their life, which is full of excitement and sounds like a valuable part of human life. That certain period caused the writer to open the inner world of his characters more deeply, to study and analyze their relationship to nature and society. From this point of view, along with Abdurauf-uncle Ahmadbek, Abduvahid-uncle Munavvarshah, Ziya-grandfather's character from the story "Old People" is interesting. He is a man who has worked in construction for years, now he is old, he receives a pension, but he does not withdraw from the worries of life. And because he loves life, he looks for ways to improve it, he gets rid of greed and immorality. He sees the meaning of life in honesty and honesty and being a partner in people's grief (5, p. 89).

Each story of the writer is shaped according to his creative intention, and the issue of unity of form and content is fully observed. If the story "SoziMunavvar" begins with a romantic description of the beautiful nature of the mountain villages, and then the author's purpose is realized, which consists of the love story of Munavvarshah and Munavvarbegim, the story "Friends' court" immediately focuses on the main issues, that is, the friend's court, in which The discussion of the behavior of the driver-Sabir will be discussed. In the story "SoziMunavvar", the threads of the SoziMunavvar tell about the youth and eternity of love and the great power of human love (2, p. 97). With the affirmative power of his melody, Munavar opens the eyes of those around him to the goodness of the earth, man and nature, because these heart-rending songs do not only express the love of one heart, but also tell of pure human love. From one story to another, FazliddinMohammadiev pays more attention to the artistic depiction of thoughts,

feelings and emotions of the characters. It is from here that in the story "The Day of the Funeral of UstoAqil" it takes a more psychological position and leads to the investigation and solution of an important social issue.

There are many people like Master Aqil in the society, but Master AqilFazliddinMuhammadiev is a craftsman and master flower maker, but he does not teach his art to anyone until the end of his life, and he does not even train any students, that is, he betrays his profession, and the writer's logical conclusion is that People will never forgive the sins of such people (2. P.87).

FazliddinMohammadiev has written a series of good comic stories during his more than twenty years of work, the best of which are "The Innovator", "Minbar and Sweeper", "UstoGaraj" and "The First Speech of the Slave-Poor". His satire not only criticizes people with broken ideas, but also treats them like a surgeon. In his humorous stories, the writer looks at his heroes as if from a secluded corner, and writes down their strangest and most ridiculous situations (1, p. 575).

This, of course, requires immense love, patience and courage from the artist towards his profession.

Thus, the attraction of FazliddinMohammadiev's pen lies in the fact that he turns to the most important topic of literature - the spiritual world of man, social ethics, and explores new aspects of it in his works. It is extremely difficult to capture such a topic and to complete it in accordance with the requirements of the era. Elements of morality - such as loyalty, love, paternal affection, etc. - appeared with man, that is, they were a bond or child of nature. Until now, man has broken thousands of chains related to nature, which he himself was tied to, and at the same time tried to make the elements of morality more complex. Because a person is, first of all, a person with his morals.

When we read the works of the writer, we come to the conclusion that man is not a slave to nature, but stands above it and walks the path between the planets. The characters of FazliddinMohammadiev seek the meaning of life, their status and a person's view of life, which has always been the source of literature, exactly from this place, from human morality.

The struggle of the writer is for the purity of the society, for the moral integrity and spirituality of a perfect human being. Each of us young people can learn from these writings of F. We should learn from Mohammadiev.

REFERENCES

1. ХудойназарАсозода. «Таърихи адабиётиточик» - Душанбе, Маорифвафарҳанг, 2014.
2. Муҳаммадиев Ф. «СозиМунаввар»- Душанбе, Маориф, 2016.
3. АсрориСомонӣваМачид Салим «АдибониТоҷикисто»
(маълумотномаи мухтасари шарҳи ҳоли)- Душанбе, Адиб, 2014.
4. Муҳаммадиев Ф. «Осоримунтахаб» -Душанбе, Адиб, 1990.
5. Муҳаммадиев Ф. «Одамони кӯҳна». -Душанбе, Ирфон, 2022.
6. Муҳаммадиев Ф. «Дӯстонтоҷисар». -Душанбе, Ирфон, 1995.